

**INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FOR CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS IN THE INTERNALLY
DISPLACED PERSONS (IDP) CAMPS IN PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study investigated inclusive education provision for children in IDP camps in Plateau State, Nigeria. One school that takes care of displaced children was selected for the study. Out of the population of 90 students (including three with special needs) and 6 teachers, using the purposive sampling technique, the researcher selected 72 students including teachers as a sample for the study. This number included three students who have some disabilities and are living in IDP camps and those who were coming from their homes. Five research questions guided the study, data for the study was collected using the researcher-made questionnaire developed to elicit responses that will provide answers to the research questions. The data was analysed using a simple percentage. The results showed among others that the conflict has a serious effect on the academic performance of displaced children with special needs and that the children participated actively in class activities. The study concluded that special needs children living in the IDP camps are faced with many challenges in the inclusive school which has a serious effect on their academic performance.

Keywords: Inclusive education; Internally displaced persons; Children with special needs

Introduction

The statistics on the impact of violence/war on education are unclear, but as far back as 2011, there were an estimated 10.5 million refugees around the world, about 27.5 million forcefully displaced within their own countries, 19.5 million of these numbers are children (Basic education coalition 2015). However, this number instead of decreasing has continued to increase, the Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (IDMC) (2022) states that 59.1 million people were living in internal displacement. This number also includes children who are supposed to be in school pursuing their education at different levels. The United Nations Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement (2019) defines Internal Displaced Persons as “persons or groups of persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular as a result of or to avoid the effects of armed conflicts, situations of generalized violence, violation of human rights or natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed national border” The basic thing in inclusive education is that it is an attempt to address the barriers to education that are deeply entrenched in social and professional attitudes, values and misconceptions about diversity (Ainscow and Miles 2009) which often determines acceptance or alienation of others. Alongside their disabilities and unprecedented socially stigmatizing labels eg “IDPs” children with special needs in the IDP camps whether they have special needs or not may encounter non-normative and potentially exclusionary social-cultural experiences in the new locations, this may lead to physical integration without social integration (Dryden-Peterson, 2011).

The Nigerian government has made giant strides in the education of persons with disabilities over the years. This is evident from the different policies from segregation to integration, from integration to mainstreaming, and from mainstreaming now to inclusive education, all in a bid to make sure that children with special needs are properly taken care of. Inclusive education according to the Federal Ministry of Education (2017) is the process of addressing all barriers and providing access to quality education to meet the diverse needs of all learners in the

same environment. Inclusive education involves the bringing together of persons with disabilities and those who do not have any disability to study in the same classroom with adaptable facilities and equipment. Nigeria developed a national policy on inclusive education in 2017 with the help of the activities of civil society groups and technical support from the Department for International Development DFID and the education sector support program in Nigeria ESSPIN 2006 – 2016. This program was approved in 2017. The policy contained guidelines for action at federal and state levels for all stakeholders in the education of persons with disabilities. Since then, all states in the federation have been asked to domesticate inclusive education in their own education policies. Plateau state is one of the states that domesticated inclusive education into their own education policies. Children in the IDP camps whether they have any disability or not constitute a special population that need special attention because some of them have missed school for some time and so it will be difficult for them to progress at the same rate as their age mates. Children in the IDP camps may not benefit maximally from this policy. The IDPs are vulnerable to further displacements, and other protection risks such as lack of access to basic services including education. They have the right to enjoy the same human rights equally with every citizen of the country.

Background

Plateau state for some years now has been battling with the issue of insecurity, this is a result of farmers/ herders clashes, attacks by unknown gunmen, and religious and ethno-communal clashes. These clashes have led to the displacement of many people from their homes and communities and are living in internally displaced persons camps in places that are said to be safe. Many of these people have had their homes, properties and schools destroyed in the wake of the crisis. The duration of stay in the IDP camps may be short or long depending on when the conflict will be over but some of these people may never have the opportunity of returning to their ancestral land again because their lands have already been occupied by the herders. The Plateau State Emergency Management Agency (SEMA) director in an interview with the news agency of Nigeria monitored by Premium Times on 9/7/2018 stated that as of July 9, 2018, there were 38,051 internally displaced persons IDPs in 31 camps as a result of the vicious attacks on communities in the state on 23rd and 24th June, 2018. The attacks took place in parts of Barakin Ladi, Bokkos, Riyom, Jos South, and Mangu local government areas. According to the SEMA director, Barakin Ladi had 16,885 IDPs in 11 camps, Jos South had 9,661 IDPs in Geo science camps A and B while Bokkos and Riyom had 2,772 persons in four camps and 2,086 in six camps respectively. The report also claimed that 6,653 persons were taking refuge in eight camps in host communities in the Mangu local government area.

Similarly, the International Organisation for Migration IOM (2020) reported that Plateau State hosted 80,970 IDPs, the highest number came from Riyom LGA with 12,691 followed by Langtang North with 11,272 and Kanke with 7,894. A report written for the news agency of Nigeria by Agas (2022) states that Bassa LGA has been attacked more than 73 times between 2015 and 2021, with the worst affected area as the Miango district of the Irigwe chieftdom. Among those affected in this area according to SEMA are over 3,000 children of school going age. Similarly, there were attacks on some communities by bandits in Kanam LGA on 11/4/2022. Mathew Ogune reporting for the Guardian newspaper states that the communities attacked are, Kyaram, Gyambau, Dungur, Kukawa and Shuwaka. SEMA states that the attack left over 4,800 IDPs including women and children taking refuge in Garga Central Primary School. It is worthy of note that children of school age constituted a great number of the people in the IDP camps having their educational program distorted due to the conflicts. Mazawi (2008) states that societal fragmentation and dissolution of governments following social violence/wars adversely affect educational systems. Among the children affected are children with special needs. Children with special needs according to the Jamaica Association for the Deaf (2015) are children who have a disability or a combination of disabilities that make learning or other activities difficult. They include those who have mental retardation, speech and language impairment, physical disabilities like visual impairment, hearing impairment, cerebral palsy, learning

disabilities etc who need special education services delivered to them in the IDP camp just like other children who are not displaced.

Unfortunately, marginalization of children in areas affected by conflicts has not been given relative attention within the inclusive education agenda (UNESCO – IIEP 2009). They are marginalized due to violent displacements and relocations from their former places of living, their education arrangement is not given the same attention as those in the regular schools. This has a serious implication for post-conflict reconstruction, (Ma, 2008). Yet how teachers negotiate inclusive education practices for children affected by conflict can be interesting because according to Oduol (2014), the global demand for good governance for instance provides prescriptions for educational practices that may constrain teachers' attention to contextual reality and priorities. Also, persistent overemphasis on narrow cognitive competencies research findings that to conflict-affected may value multiple forms of learning (Winthrop and Kirk 2008). All these attacks and subsequent displacement of the people have caused setbacks in access to education forcing the affected children to lag behind among their peers in academics. The consequence of this is that the schools in the host community will not be able to accommodate the number of school-aged children in their schools as a result of the increase in the number of displaced children in the community. The aim of this paper is to find out how children with special needs living in IDP camps are provided with inclusive education services and the effect of the conflict on their academic performance.

Significance of the study

The findings of this study will be beneficial to the state universal basic education boards, state emergency management agencies, host communities and people living in IDP camps.

Research questions

To help in the conduct of this study, the researcher sought answers to the following questions:

- i. To what extent has the conflict affected the academic performance of displaced special needs children in the IDP camps?
- ii. How will you rate the participation of displaced special needs children in the class?
- iii. What category/categories of children with special needs do you have in your school?
- iv. What is the attitude/direction of other children towards the displaced children in your school?
- v. What are some of the challenges faced by the displaced special needs children in the school?

Methodology

The population for this study includes all the children in IDP camps in Plateau state. Study made use of the cross-sectional survey to select a representative sample from the population for the study. From this population, using the convenient or purposive sampling technique, the researcher selected one school that is currently providing educational services to children of internally displaced persons in one of the most affected areas in Miango district of Irigwe chiefdom. The school, Calvary Arrow Nursery and Primary Academy Miango was established in 2020 mainly to take care of displaced and less privileged children. The reason for selecting this school is that most of the IDP camps at the time of this research were not providing any educational services for the IDP children. The school has students in both nursery one to primary four. The school has a population of 90 students among 46 displaced children and only six teachers were teaching the students in this school. Three of the 46 students have disabilities that require a special education programme. From the population, the researcher decided to select all the 46 displaced children, all the six teachers and 20 students from the primary classes that are not displaced as participants for the study giving a total of 72. The instrument used for data collection is a researcher-made questionnaire. The researcher after obtaining permission from the school gave the questionnaires to the headmaster who distributed them to the students and teachers. The researcher came back after one week to collect the

completed questionnaires. This means that the respondents were allowed to take the questionnaire home for their parents or senior brothers or sisters to help record their responses for them.

Data analysis

The data collected was analysed using simple percentages and it was based on the research questions raised above. The results are displayed in tables.

Research question 1. To what extent has the conflict affected the academic performance of the displaced special needs children in your school?

Table 1 shows the extent to which conflict has affected the academic performance of displaced children

S/N	Effects of conflict on academic performance	No. of resp.	Percentage
1	Very serious effect	42	58
2	Serious effect	25	35
3	Mild effect	05	07
4	No effect at all	00	00
Total		72	100

Table 1 shows that 42(58%) of the respondents indicated that the conflict has a very serious effect on their academic performance, 25(35%) indicated that the crisis has a serious effect on their academic performance, 5 (7%) of the respondents indicated that the conflict-affected them mildly. None of the respondents indicated that the conflict had any effect on their academic performance

Research question 2. How will you rate the participation of the displaced special needs children in the class?

Table 2 shows the participation of displaced children in classwork

Displaced children's participation in class	Frequency	Percentage
participates very actively	34	47.2
participates actively	22	30.6
participates inactively	12	16,7
participates very inactively	04	5.6
Total	72	100

Table 2 above shows that 34(47.2%) of the respondents indicated that the displaced children participate actively in class, 22(30.6%) of the respondents indicated that the displaced students participate actively while 12(16.7%) of the respondents indicated that the displaced children participation in class is inactive while 4(5.6%) indicated that their participation is very inactive.

Research question 3: What category/categories of children with special needs do you have in your school?

Table 3 shows the categories of children with special needs in the IDP attending school

S/N	Cat. of displaced children with special needs	No. of resp.	Percentage
1	Visually impaired	0	0
2	Hearing impaired	0	0
3	Physical handicaps	3	100
4	Mentally retarded	0	0
Total		3	100

Table 3 shows that there is no student with visual impairment, Hearing impairment, mental retardation in the school. The table also shows that there are 3(100%) of the students in the school with different types of physical handicaps.

Research question 4. What is the attitude/direction of other children towards the displaced children in your school?

Table 4 shows the attitude of other children towards the displaced children

Attitudes of other students towards displaced children	Frequency	Percentage
positive	42	58.3
Neutral	22	30.5
negative	08	11.1
Total	72	100

Table 4 above shows that 42(58.3%) of the respondents indicated the attitude of fellow students towards the displaced children is positive, 22(30.6%) indicated that the attitude of their fellow students is neutral while 8(11.1%) of the respondents believe that the attitude of the fellow students is negative

Research question 5. What are some of the challenges faced by the displaced special needs children in the school?

Figure 1. shows ten of the challenges faced by the displaced children in the school

S/N	Factors	Freq.	%
1	Mobility	8	11.1
2	Attitude of teachers	1	1.3
3	Lack of classes	11	15.3
4	Lack of drinking water	4	5.6
5	Lack of teachers	9	12.5
6	Lack of textbooks	8	11.1
7	Lack of writing materials (biro and pencil)	7	9.7
8	Attitude of our classmates	2	2.8
9	Fear of attack	11	15.3
10	Hunger	11	15.3
TOTAL		52	100

Figure 1 shows ten problems most frequently cited by respondents as the problems they face in the school. The five most cited problems were: fear of attack (15.3%), hunger (15.3%) and lack of classes (15.3%). The second most frequently cited problem is a lack of teachers (12.5), lack of textbooks 11.1%, lack of writing materials (9.7%) and mobility 11.1%. The least cited by the respondents are lack of drinking water 3(5.8%), attitude of classmates 2.8%, and attitude of teachers 1.3%. The figure showed that displaced students were faced with some challenges in the school.

Findings and discussion

The findings in this paper are presented according to the issues raised for investigation.

Effect of conflict on the academic performance of displaced special needs children

This study has discovered that the conflict has a serious impact on the academic performance of displaced children in IDP camps, 61.52% of the respondents agreed that the conflict has a very serious effect on their academic performance while 28.85% said that the conflict have a serious effect on their academic performance and 9.61% believed that conflict only affected them mildly giving a total of 100% of respondents agreeing that the conflict has effect on their academic performance. The result shows that 90.37% of the respondents believe that the conflict has serious negative effects on their academic performance. Many of them stated that they had to stay out of school for some time before coming to this school, consequently, they are behind their age mates who were not affected by the crisis. Many of the respondents state that they lost everything including their books during the crisis and it is difficult for them to acquire new ones, they believe that this has seriously affected their academic performance.

Participation of the displaced special needs children in class

This study has discovered that the students participate actively in the class. That is to say that they participate in class discussions and other class activities actively. This is so because 46.2% of the respondents agree that the

students are very active and 32.7% state that they are active, this gives a total of 78.9% as against 21.1% who state that the students are not active in class. One would have thought that the displaced children would be thinking of their lost homes and properties, and therefore they may be absent-minded which would have affected their participation in class activities. However, looking at the ages of the participants, one will see that all of them are children under the age of fifteen except for the teachers who are adults, children at this age can easily forget what happened since they are not thinking of how to get food or clothing or even thinking of how to settle down.

Category/categories of children with special needs in the school

The study discovered that only 3 (5.8%) of the students have different handicapping conditions. These students are those who have different types of physical handicaps including those with crippling conditions. Of all other students, 94.2% are those who do not have any handicapping conditions.

The attitude of other children towards the displaced special needs children in the school

The result of the study shows that most of the respondents 84.6% have positive attitudes towards children with special needs in the school. This is demonstrated in the way they assist the students in the school. However, 15.4% of the respondents have a neutral attitude towards the students with disabilities while 17% of the respondents believed that the attitude of the students towards those that have special needs is negative. Those who have neutral attitudes towards persons with disabilities stated that they do not know much about people living with disabilities. With enlightenment from the school, they may change their attitude. Many of those who have negative attitudes are those who came into the school newly, they never had anything to do with people with disabilities before and so they disliked them. It is also believed that their attitude will change in due course as they continue to interact with them in the school.

Some of the challenges faced by the displaced children in the school

No doubt about this that the displaced children are facing different problems, the study only concerned itself with the problems faced by the students in the school as expressed by the respondents. The study discovered that the displaced children are faced with different problems in the school that make learning uncomfortable for them. The most serious problem is the lack of classes 15.3% as a result of the number of students that relocated from the affected areas, the classes available in the school cannot contain them. Another problem cited by the respondents is fear of another attack, most of the respondents still believe that where they are is still not safe, their past experience is still fresh in their minds. The least of the problems are the attitude of classmates and the attitude of their teachers. The attitude of the teachers is the least problem cited by the respondents, cited by only 1.3% of the respondents. One cannot but be surprised with this result because the school was first set up as a missionary school so all the staff members are those who have keyed into the vision of love for all, including those in dire need. The students also are taught to love one another irrespective of who the person is or the condition the person finds himself/herself in.

Conclusion

Every child has the constitutional right to education wherever the child is and under whatever circumstance. Children in the IDP camps, those with disabilities and those without any, have the right to inclusive education as their counterparts anywhere in any school in the state. This study has revealed some of the issues in the provision of inclusive education for displaced children living in IDP camps. Children's views that the conflict has a serious effect on their academic performances were clearly stated. However, despite the effect of the conflict on the academic performance of the displaced children, the children believed that the effect of the conflict did not affect their class participation. The provision of inclusive education to displaced children is met with some challenges that the children, teachers and school authorities will always battle with.

References

- Ainscow, M., and Miles, S. (2019). Developing Inclusive Education System: how can we move policies forward? University of Manchester.
- Basic Education Coalition (2015). Educating refugees and IDPs http://www.basiced.org/wpcontent/uploads/factsheets/educating_refugees_and_IDPs_pdf
- Dryden-Peterson, S. (2011). Conflict, education and displacement. *An Interdisciplinary Journal of Conflict and Education* 1, 1 – 15
- Federal Ministry of Education (2017). National Policy on Inclusive Education in Nigeria. Retrieved from, www.academia.edu/.../last final draft/INCLUSIVE EDUCATIONPOLICYfeb.
- Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre IDMC (2022). Retrieved from <https://www.internal-displacement.org/>
- International Organisation for Migrants: Displacement tracking matrix in North Central zone retrieved from <http://www.iom.int/> and%20North%20west%20report%pdf?file=1&type=node&id=10351
- Jamaica Association for the Deaf (2015). Who are the children with special needs retrieved from <https://www.jamdeaf.org.jm/articles/who-are-the-children-with-special-needs>
- Ma, S. (2008). From tension to violence: identities and perceptions in Kenya’s post-education conflict. devNet conference, African perspective 3rd – 5th Dec. 2008.
- Martha Agas 2022. *Addressing the educational needs of victims of conflicts in Plateau IDP camps*. News Agency of Nigeria August 30, 2022 <https://africanews.com/2022/08/01/feature/addressing-educational-needs-of-victims-of-conflicts-in-plateau-idp-camps/>
- Mathew O. (2022). Over 4,800 The Guardian newspaper article 13/4/2022 <https://guardian.ng/news/nigeria/over4800-persons-displaced-by-plateau-state-attacks-humanitarian-minister/>
- Mazawi, A. E., (2008). Dis/integrated orders and the politics of recognition: civil upheavals, militarism, and education lives and work. *Mediterranean Journal of Educational Studies* 13(2) 69 – 89.
- Oduol, T. (2014). The challenges of ethical leadership: A case study of secondary school leader’s experiences in Kenya. Wellington: Victoria University of Wellington.
- Plateau State Emergency Management Agency SEMA 2018. Over 38,000 IDPs in 31 camps in Plateau – SEMA Premium Times news article 9/7/2018 <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/regional/north-central/275502-killings-over-3,8000-idps-in-31-camps-plateau-sema.html>
- UNESCO: International Institute for Education Planning (2009). Reaching the marginalized: Educational marginalization in national education Plans. Global monitoring report.
- United Nations Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement (2019). Retrieved from <https://rli.blogs.sas.ac.uk/2019/04/04/the-un-guiding-principles-on-internal-displacement-the-extent-to-which-the-protection-of-idps-has-been-advanced/>
- Winthrop, R. & Kirk, J. (2008). Learning for a bright future: schooling, armed conflict and children’s well-being. *Comparative and International Education Society* 52(4) 629 –661.